

GEO MORPHOMETRY
PERUGIA ITALY

2025
JUNE 9-13

Influence of Data Resolution on Logistic Regression Models for Landslide Susceptibility in Tropical Environments

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Abstract - In February 2023, an extreme rainfall event on the northern coast of São Sebastião, southeastern Brazil, delivered over 450 mm of rainfall within 24 hours, triggering widespread landslides with severe social and environmental impacts. This study evaluates landslide susceptibility using Logistic Regression (LR) across three model configurations: M1 (trained and tested on 5 m data from a high-resolution Digital Surface Model), M2 (trained and tested on 30 m Copernicus DEM data), and M3 (trained on 5 m data and tested on 30 m data). Morphometric parameters (slope, aspect, curvatures, and Topographic Position Index) were derived using WhiteboxTools. M2 demonstrated superior performance, achieving the highest ROC AUC (78.40%) and accuracy (70.67%), underscoring its suitability for regional-scale analyses. In contrast, M1 captured finer spatial details but showed lower AUC (71.01%) and accuracy (66.30%), reflecting challenges in balancing resolution and generalization. M3 exhibited a notable trade-off: high sensitivity (recall = 80.34%) for landslide detection but reduced precision (67.19%), emphasizing the complexities of applying high-resolution models to coarser data. These results highlight the critical role of data resolution in landslide susceptibility modeling. While high-resolution data (M1) excels in local-scale precision, lower-resolution data (M2) offers robust regional insights. M3 bridges these scales but reveals inherent limitations, such as increased false positives. The generated maps provide actionable tools for disaster risk mitigation, particularly in data-scarce regions. This work underscores the need to align model resolution with application goals, balancing detail and generalizability for effective landslide risk management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Landslides are among the most destructive natural hazards, causing significant social, economic, and environmental impacts worldwide. These events are often triggered by a combination of factors, such as intense rainfall, steep terrain, and geological and soil characteristics, frequently exacerbated by human activities. In this context, landslide susceptibility mapping plays a critical role in disaster risk reduction, providing essential support for land-use planning and the development of early warning systems.

In recent years, machine learning (ML) and classical statistical methods have become indispensable for landslide susceptibility modeling. Logistic Regression (LR), a statistical approach widely integrated into ML workflows, has proven particularly valuable due to its computational efficiency, interpretability, and capacity to handle diverse spatial datasets. While complex ML models (e.g., neural networks, decision trees) may excel in capturing non-linear relationships, recent research highlights that simpler, interpretable methods like LR remain competitive in geospatial applications [1], especially when balancing predictive performance with operational practicality. This versatility positions LR as a pragmatic choice for multi-scale landslide risk assessments, where transparency and adaptability to varying data resolutions are critical.

The Serra do Mar mountain range, located along the southeastern coast of Brazil, is characterized by steep slopes, dense vegetation, and frequent landslides. These natural processes are intensified by the region's geomorphological conditions and high rainfall levels, which have historically contributed to catastrophic events resulting in significant social and economic losses [2][3]. Despite this history, the development of accurate susceptibility models in the region faces challenges related to the limited availability of high-resolution data, the absence of comprehensive landslide inventories, and the scarcity of detailed historical records.

Although machine learning techniques have proven effective in other regions, their application to the Serra do Mar remains largely unexplored. Addressing these gaps is essential for improving susceptibility models and strengthening risk mitigation strategies in the region. In this context, this study conducts a comparative analysis of two digital elevation models: a high-resolution 5 m Digital Surface Model (DSM) and a global 30 m Digital Elevation Model (DEM). The main objective is to evaluate the performance of models trained with high-resolution data when applied to lower-resolution datasets. The analysis focuses on the São Sebastião region, aiming to assess the scalability of the models and identify the limitations and potential benefits associated with using data at different spatial resolutions.

II. STUDY AREA

In February 2023, São Sebastião, located on the northern coast of the Serra do Mar, experienced an extreme rainfall event with over 450 mm of precipitation recorded within a 24-hour period. This unprecedented event triggered widespread shallow landslides (Fig. 1), resulting in severe social, economic, and environmental consequences. Most of the landslides were concentrated along the steep escarpments, where natural vulnerability is heightened by the region's geomorphological characteristics and shallow soil profiles.

III. METHODS

For the comparison between different models, two DSMs with distinct spatial resolutions were used: a 5 m DSM provided by the São Paulo State Government (IDE-DSM) [4] and the Copernicus DEM (Cop-DEM) with a spatial resolution of 30 meters [5].

The landslide inventory consists of 1,068 records representing documented locations of landslide events within the

study area [6]. To develop the susceptibility models, an equivalent set of absence points (1,068) was generated through random sampling using QGIS software, representing areas without documented landslides. These absence points were integrated into the landslide inventory, resulting in a balanced dataset for model training and evaluation (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Location of the Study Area and Samples Distribution. A) Detailed view of landslide points within the study area, overlaid on a high-resolution background image

The morphometric parameters used in this study - slope, aspect, curvatures, and Topographic Position Index (TPI) - were extracted from the rasters using WhiteboxTools [7]. Based on these data, three model configurations were developed using LR: (M1) Model trained and tested on 5 m data (IDE-DSM), (M2) Model trained and tested on 30 m data (Cop-DEM), (M3) Model trained on 5 m data and tested on 30 m data (IDE-DSM to Cop-DEM).

LR establishes a relationship between a dependent variable and multiple predictor variables (independent variables), allowing the inclusion of continuous, discrete, or mixed data types without requiring normal distribution. Recognized as a widely accepted statistical approach, LR has been extensively applied in landslide susceptibility modeling, demonstrating its effectiveness across various geographic and environmental contexts [8][9].

The landslide susceptibility maps generated from the three models were evaluated using statistical metrics calculated by the

Python programming language. This process involved a suite of Python libraries: Rasterio for raster data processing, NumPy for numerical and matrix operations, Pandas for data management and analysis, Scikit-learn for implementing Logistic Regression, and Matplotlib for data visualization.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results revealed significant differences in performance across the models. M2 achieved the highest accuracy (0.7067) and ROC AUC (0.7840), demonstrating robustness for regional-scale analyses (Table I). In contrast, M1 captured finer spatial patterns (Fig. 2A) but underperformed in accuracy (0.6630) and ROC AUC (0.7101), reflecting challenges in balancing high-resolution detail with generalization. Despite this, M1 exhibited moderate capability in detecting localized instability (recall = 0.6442; F1-score = 0.6604). Notably, M3 demonstrated the highest sensitivity (recall = 0.8034), suggesting strong utility for landslide detection, albeit with reduced precision (0.6719) compared to M2 (Table I).

TABLE 1. PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODELS ACROSS TRAINING AND PREDICTION SPATIAL RESOLUTIONS

Model	Train Data	Pred Data	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	ROC AUC
M1	5 m	5 m	0.6630	0.6774	0.6442	0.6604	0.7101
M2	30 m	30 m	0.7067	0.7054	0.7270	0.7160	0.7840
M3	5 m	30 m	0.7055	0.6719	0.8034	0.7318	0.7565

In contrast, M3 demonstrated the highest sensitivity (recall = 0.8034), suggesting its efficacy in detecting landslide-susceptible areas. However, this model exhibited a modest decline in overall performance (AUC = 0.7565), reflecting the capacity of high-resolution-trained models to retain predictive capability when applied to lower-resolution data. The reduction in precision (0.6719) indicates a greater tendency for false positives, a critical limitation for practical applications. These findings align with studies highlighting challenges in cross-resolution model transfer, particularly increased false positives and reduced precision when applying high-resolution-trained models to coarser datasets [10].

A visual analysis of the susceptibility maps revealed notable

spatial distinctions (Fig. 2). M1 (Fig. 2A) demonstrated superior capability in identifying critical zones, with fragmented high-susceptibility areas and well-defined boundaries. However, reliance on a DSM introduced noise from anthropogenic features (e.g., roads, rooftops). In contrast, M2 (Fig. 2B) exhibited broader generalization, with continuous high-susceptibility regions that may oversimplify localized geomorphic characteristics.

Figure 2. Landslide susceptibility maps: (A) M1 (trained and tested on 5 m data, IDE-DSM), (B) M2 (trained and tested on 30 m data, Copernicus DEM), (C) M3 (trained on 5 m data and tested on 30 m data, IDE-DSM to Cop-DEM)

Conversely, M3 (Fig. 2C) exhibited an intermediate pattern, retaining some detail from M1 while demonstrating smoothing effects due to the lower resolution of the applied raster. This analysis underscores the importance of aligning data resolution with study objectives, as emphasized by recent studies on spatial resolution in landslide susceptibility mapping [11].

The results highlight the relevance of high-resolution data for local-scale analyses and detailed mapping, essential for urban planning and risk mitigation. M1 demonstrated stronger performance in metrics such as F1-score (0.6604) and AUC (0.7101), reflecting its ability to capture localized susceptibility patterns in areas with pronounced topographic variation. In contrast, M2 proved more suitable for regional applications, where spatial generalization enhances robustness. However, M3 demonstrated potential for cross-resolution applications, albeit with trade-offs such as increased false positives (precision = 0.6719).

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study underscores the critical influence of data resolution on landslide susceptibility modeling, revealing distinct trade-offs between spatial detail and generalizability. M2 emerged as the optimal choice for regional-scale applications, where robustness and noise reduction (e.g., roads, buildings) are prioritized. In contrast, M1 demonstrated strengths in capturing fine-scale topographic patterns, albeit with

limitations in broader generalization. M3 bridged these scales, highlighting the potential and challenges of transferring high-resolution models to coarser data, as evidenced by its high sensitivity but elevated false positives.

These findings advocate for context-driven resolution selection: high-resolution data for localized precision, lower resolution for regional insights, and hybrid approaches to harmonize these strengths. Future work should focus on optimizing cross-resolution compatibility to enhance model adaptability in data-scarce environments.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support provided by CAPES (Finance code 001) and FAPESP (#2023/11197-1).

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